

APPLICATION OF CREATIVE THINKING IN RUSSIAN LANGUAGE LESSONS IN NON-LINGUISTIC UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract: In the modern educational process, learning should be interesting, effective and diverse. For this purpose, various methods and techniques are used, demonstrating the professional competence of the teacher. This article examines the use of creative thinking in Russian language lessons in non-linguistic universities.

Key words: creative thinking, Russian language, methods and techniques, students of non-linguistic universities, modern education.

1 Introduction

Creative thinking is an important aspect of functional literacy, which means a person's ability to use their imagination to form and improve ideas, thoughts, as well as to create new knowledge and solve problems that they have not encountered before.

The concept of "creative thinking" was first proposed by the famous scientist J. Guilford. In his works, he noted that creative thinking is one of the forms of thinking that manifests itself in the creation of new products and new formations in the process of cognition, as well as in solving various problems, forming unusual and original ideas, generalizations and theories [1].

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, there are serious demands on the morale, intellectual potential and professionalism of teachers. In this regard, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev said: "A teacher must meet high standards, he must have high qualities." From the above, one can understand the content of the requirements for the personality of a modern teacher. Creativity is often only in words, but in fact, most universities are currently experiencing a "creative gap" when much more creative activity occurs outside the educational process. Many researchers argue that creativity is not just an enrichment or addition to the classroom: it is a definable, measurable set of psychological skills that improve learning and will be needed in the XXI century workforce.

Help students understand when it is appropriate to be creative. For example, help them see contexts in which creativity is more or less useful - in a low-stakes group project versus a standardized state assessment. Use creative teaching strategies, models, and methods as much as possible in a variety of areas. Model students' creativity in how they speak and act. For example, you might say, "I've thought of three ways to teach this lesson. I'll show you two, and then you can come up with a third," or show them a personal project you've been working on [2].

The benefits of a creative approach to learning are numerous: from developing communication skills to the ability to see unconventional solutions in everyday situations. In the age of digital technologies and global challenges, creativity is becoming the key to successful adaptation and professional growth. Therefore, it is important that modern educational systems include the development of creative skills as part of the learning process, preparing students for effective work and creativity in the future.

Developing students' creativity in Russian language lessons in non-linguistic universities is an important task for a teacher in terms of modern education, since it promotes the development of innovative and problem-oriented skills, flexibility of thinking and the ability to find new solutions. The teacher's activity, in the Russian language studies in the lessons using creative thinking, is aimed at developing the student's personality, their creative abilities, at forming an interest in learning the subject, as well as the desire to learn and think beautifully, unconventionally, and most importantly correctly [3]. Teachers with professional competence play a key role in developing the creativity of students of non-linguistic universities. There are various methods and techniques that help teachers demonstrate their competence:

It is important that teachers are open to new ideas, ready for self-development and continuous learning in order to effectively develop students' creative abilities.

2 Technology for obtaining materials and research method

Developing creative thinking in students of non-linguistic universities requires the use of innovative methods and techniques. Interactive techniques and creative tasks play a key role in this, stimulating students to actively participate in the learning process and encouraging them to be inventive and explore. For example, the project method, role-playing games and brainstorming encourage students to think outside the box, look for original solutions and collaborate with others.

Feedback and self-assessment also play an important role in developing creativity, helping students to recognize their strengths and areas for improvement. Receiving regular constructive feedback from teachers and classmates, as well as the ability to critically evaluate one's own work, contribute to the growth of confidence in their creative abilities.

The use of these methods in the educational process not only enriches the learning experience, but also prepares students for a successful life and career in an ever-changing world, where creativity and innovative thinking are key competencies.

Creative thinking finds its application in a wide range of fields of knowledge, from the natural sciences to the humanities. In the natural sciences, creativity can mean using unconventional experiments and research methods to discover new phenomena and laws of nature. For example, using virtual reality to visualize complex biological processes or creating innovative models to study atomic structures. In the humanities, creativity can be demonstrated through the integration of art and technology into the learning process, for example, through the creation of multimedia projects that allow for a deeper understanding of historical events or literary works. Innovations in teaching the humanities also include the development of interactive courses that stimulate critical thinking and discussion, allowing students to actively participate in the learning process and apply theoretical knowledge in practice.

3 Experimental results and their discussion

The modern education system rejects traditional teaching, strives and requires the introduction of new technologies, ideas, creativity on the part of the teacher, various kinds of teaching methods such as: didactic

games, competitions, open lessons, debates, round tables, etc. Therefore, based on this, we can determine that more and more attention is paid to the development of creative abilities, creativity of primary school age.

Creative thinking is characterized by four main qualities. Let's highlight them in the form of a diagram:

Russian language lessons in non-linguistic universities contribute to the effective development of students' creative thinking, since for students, the perception of the literary world is based on the dissemination of all kinds of events, facts and phenomena of reality and the creation of elements of a new world, which, in essence, corresponds to the peculiarities of the processes of imagination, creative thinking and creative activity, that is, a set of areas of development of creative thinking.

Each of us has encountered creativity, and it has played an important role in our lives, discovering something new. According to many scientists, creativity is the main component in the lessons. For example, the famous psychologist A. Vygotsky wrote: "Creativity is the lot of a few select people, geniuses, talents who have created great works of art, made a great scientific discovery or invented some improvement in the field of technology"[4]. There are many methods and technologies that allow students to develop creative and imaginative aspects when studying the Russian language. These methods include:

The "brainstorming" method - this method is aimed at ensuring that students of non-linguistic universities work in a group to solve a specific problem. For example:

1. Using role-playing games and improvisation. Students can play the roles of characters from the book and act in accordance with their characters and situations from the book;
2. Creating an alternative ending. Students can offer their own options for plot development and discuss them with the class;
3. Using creative methods of text analysis, such as creating collages or illustrations for the text;
4. Conducting discussions about moral dilemmas and ethical issues raised in a particular story, fairy tale, etc.;
5. Conducting creative competitions related to a book, a work, for example, writing a sequel or adapting a plot to another genre.
7. Using technology to view multimedia presentations or videos related to the book.
8. Organizing dramatized readings or performances of excerpts from stories and fairy tales.
10. Using creative writing techniques, such as writing letters from one character to another or creating a character diary.

The method of associating ideas is aimed at using the capabilities of the human senses (hearing, sight, touch) and its mental abilities to form new ideas. By observing, listening or testing a certain object, a junior schoolchild is able to find the unknown from the known, to understand another from one object, while having similarities and differences [5].

The method of inversion is aimed at finding ideas for solving a creative problem in new, non-traditional directions.

The Delphi method is aimed at solving problems using interviews and surveys. This method takes place in 3 stages:

Method "Six hats"

This method is aimed at developing attentiveness, when using this method, it is necessary: to put on 6 hats of different colors:

Classical methods are only the initial step for improving standard creative thinking. But in order to fully achieve the development of creative thinking in students, we use different tasks and exercises in lessons. I will share my experience of using techniques in reading lessons that contribute to the development of creative thinking. When conducting a lesson, I always planned my algorithm of work, and always in each lesson I removed 3-4 minutes for logical tasks, which, as a rule, are very interesting and activate students.

1. Association Table: An exercise aimed at developing quick reactions and finding solutions. Students are given a table with letters. Focus your gaze and remember the word you saw first. Without thinking for long, name 5 associations related to it.

2. Creative Artist: In this exercise, students will be in the role of an architect. They write on a piece of paper any 10 words that first come to mind. For example, cucumber, sun, strawberry, etc. You tell them that the listed words are mandatory conditions of the customer for whom you are designing his house and, using the analogy method, begin to fill in the area: "cucumber" - this will be an element in the rooms (green wallpaper), "sun" - this will be furniture in the kitchen, and so on. Develops imagination and creates a real house project.

3. "Looking for Anton": This is an assignment that is aimed at developing the construction of logical sequences of any events. You give the students cards with the main character Anton, who is in different places. For example, on card 1 it is shown that the boy is in the theater, on card 2 he is in the park with a

friend, etc. And the students must compare the algorithm of actions, and find out at the end where he ended up.

4 Conclusions

The traditional chalk board can no longer cope with new functions. The new generation of students who grew up on computers and mobile phones, who have a much higher need for visual information, require a different approach from the teacher. Today's university board must be interactive - this is the conclusion that everyone who meets the increasing requirements for the organization and information content of the university education process comes to. Interactive boards in practice turn out to be much more effective than traditional university boards or projects. Due to the fact that the material is presented in an interactive mode, communicative interaction with students is significantly improved, which helps to convey information to them faster and more effectively. Accordingly, the level of quality of education improves.

We can conclude that the use of creative thinking in the learning process undoubtedly causes increased interest in students of non-linguistic universities and increases motivation for learning. And economical use of time at the stages of consolidating the topic being studied and checking independent work when involving a large number of students. Also, the advantages of technical means can be considered the creation of conditions for the implementation of students' creative potential and the performance of a large amount of work in the lesson. Thus, creative thinking of students of non-linguistic universities is a personal characteristic and is the ability to generate unusual ideas, find original solutions, deviate from traditional patterns of thinking. The task of the teacher is to reveal these gifts, to create circumstances for the creative implementation of students. Thus, the use of various methods, techniques, technologies in Russian language lessons in non-linguistic universities helps students to actively engage in the creative process, develop creative thinking, imagination, fantasy, helps to see something new, independently solve the problem and correctly express their thoughts.

References

1. Guilford J. Three sides of intelligence. Psychology of thinking. Ed. -2. -M.: Progress, 2023.
2. Nurullaeva G. R. (2021). The role of teacher teaching creativity in the development of students' intelligence. Issues of science and education, (18 (143)), 73-82.
3. Murodova O.N., & Sadykov R.M. (2023). Use of information technology in russian language and reading literacy lessons in primary school. science and innovation, 2 (Special Issue 10), 667-669. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10200702
4. Khamidullaeva R.F., & Sadykov R.M. (2023). Methodology of using didactic games in russian language and reading literacy lessons in primary school. Science and innovation, 2 (Special Issue 10), 673-675. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10200727
5. Ismoiljanova U. & Sadykov R. M. (2023). Using creative thinking in reading lessons in national classrooms. Science and innovation, 2 (Special Issue 10), 659-661. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10200617